

Therapeutic Applications of Traditional Chinese Medicine in the Management of Post-Stroke Sequelae: A Narrative Review.

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Abstract

Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) is used to treat the after-effects of a stroke, using various methods such as acupuncture, cupping therapy, moxibustion, *Tui Na* massage, herbal medicine, *Qigong* and diet therapy. The objectives of this study are to analyse the existing literature on the impacts of different TCM methods in the treatment of post-stroke sequelae, identifying which have established scientific support and which require further investigation, therefore constituting a narrative review article. Acupuncture has demonstrated neuroprotective benefits by improving cerebral blood flow and decreasing neuroinflammation. Phytotherapy, using plants such as *Salvia miltiorrhiza*, *Ginkgo biloba* and *Panax notoginseng*, has demonstrated antioxidant and neuroprotective effects. *Qigong* and moxibustion can help reduce risk factors and promote nerve regeneration, while cupping and *Tui Na* massage offer benefits for pain relief and motor recovery. Diet therapy is significant in neuroplasticity and in preventing subsequent complications. In summary, TCM offers significant contributions to post-stroke rehabilitation.

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1. Introduction

Stroke is a sudden neurological condition triggered by an abrupt interruption of cerebral blood flow, which hinders sufficient oxygenation and nutrition of nerve cells, resulting in brain damage and, in some cases, patient death ^{1,2}. It is a cerebrovascular disease with high incidence (11.9 million new stroke cases worldwide, equivalent to 0.15%), mortality (10%), and disability rate (60%) ³⁻⁵.

Stroke can be categorised into two main types: ischemic and haemorrhagic. Ischemic stroke arises from the blockage of a cerebral artery by a thrombus, leading to an ischemic area and subsequently a cerebral infarction. Conversely, hemorrhagic stroke occurs as a result of the rupture of a cerebral blood vessel, causing bleeding into the brain parenchyma or the subarachnoid space. This abrupt loss of vascular integrity results in compression of adjacent brain tissue, increased intracranial pressure, and rapid onset of neurological deficits ^{2,6,7}.

The complex pathology of ischemic stroke involves a cascade of events culminating in neuronal death and necrosis in the affected region, including oxidative stress, inflammation, excitotoxicity, and activation of the complement system. In hemorrhagic stroke, several pathogenic mechanisms contribute to worsening the lesion, including blood cytotoxicity, hypermetabolism, excitotoxicity, spreading depression, oxidative stress, and inflammation. These processes lead to irreversible destruction of the neurovascular unit, collapse of the blood-brain barrier, fatal brain oedema, and widespread brain cell death.

A comprehensive understanding of these pathophysiological processes is vital to developing more effective therapeutic approaches during both the acute phase and post-stroke rehabilitation^{2,8,9}.

Due to its impact, there has been an increasing focus on the search for complementary treatments to enhance recovery by combining Western medicine with TCM¹⁰.

TCM has demonstrated numerous advantages in preventing and treating stroke sequelae, as TCM treatments improve cerebral microcirculation, relieve neurological disorders, regulate metabolism, attenuate inflammation, and reduce oxidative stress-induced injury, thereby mitigating brain damage and preventing stroke recurrence¹¹⁻¹⁴.

According to Choi *et al.*¹⁵, TCM provides several therapeutic methods for the rehabilitation and treatment of multiple pathologies. Among these, acupuncture stands out as one of the most widely recognised practices, used to treat neurological disorders, including stroke complications.

TCM has accumulated extensive clinical experience over thousands of years of medical practice. TCM researchers uphold the view that stroke causes and mechanisms stem from deficiencies in healthy *Qi* (or vital energy), dietary factors, emotions, fatigue, and internal injuries. “Healthy *Qi*” refers to a free and balanced flow, without stagnations or deficiencies, enabling the body to withstand external pathogenic factors (such as Wind, Cold, or Dampness) and maintain intact physiological functions. When *Qi* is deficient, a range of clinical manifestations may occur, including chronic fatigue, susceptibility to recurrent infections, digestive disturbances, cardiovascular complications, or even Blood stasis¹⁶.

In addition to acupuncture, other therapeutic methods—such as herbal medicine, *qigong*, moxibustion, cupping therapy, *Tui Na* massage, and dietotherapy—have shown promise in stimulating recovery and alleviating post-stroke sequelae, such as paralysis or weakness of one side of the body, aphasia, dysphagia, spasticity, depression, anxiety, and fatigue¹⁵.

Accordingly, this narrative review analyses the various treatments offered by TCM and their effects on the rehabilitation of individuals who have suffered a stroke, emphasising their benefits, challenges, and future perspectives.

2. Methodology

This research consists of a narrative literature review aimed at analysing and synthesising the roles of TCM in the treatment of post-stroke sequelae. To this end, searches were conducted in electronic databases such as PubMed, Scielo, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar.

Inclusion criteria corresponded to the selection of scientific studies focused on the use of TCM therapies, specifically acupuncture, herbal medicine, moxibustion, cupping therapy, *Tui Na* massage, *qigong*, and dietotherapy, related to the treatment of post-stroke sequelae, between 2009 and 2025. Studies presenting both clinical evidence and experimental research were considered, provided they were connected to mechanisms of action and therapeutic improvement of TCM methods in post-stroke scenarios, whether ischemic or haemorrhagic.

The research strategy involved the use of keywords such as “Traditional Chinese Medicine”, “Sequelae”, “Rehabilitation”, and “Stroke”.

After the initial selection of studies, a qualitative analysis of full texts was carried out, focusing on recognition of reported clinical advantages, underlying physiological mechanisms, methodological limitations of the studies, and future research perspectives.

3. Results

3.1. Acupuncture

Acupuncture is among the most frequently used therapeutic methods in TCM. It is a technique that treats diseases through stimulation of the skin or deeper tissues at specific sites on the body known as acupuncture points¹⁷.

In the post-stroke setting, acupuncture treatment can substantially reduce the size of the infarcted region, increase cerebral blood flow to enhance energy metabolism in the affected area, regulate blood lipid metabolism to counteract the damage caused by cerebral free radicals, inhibit apoptosis in the cerebral cortex, and minimise levels of excitatory amino acids to reduce neurotoxicity. Thus, acupuncture stimulation activates vagal activity and the cholinergic anti-inflammatory pathway, contributing to the reduction of neuroinflammation¹⁸.

According to Zhu *et al.*¹⁹, the use of acupuncture in ischemic stroke rehabilitation can stimulate relevant functional brain areas and improve neurological deficits. Their findings suggest that the therapeutic outcomes of acupuncture rehabilitation surpass those of standard Western medical treatment and are more effective in relieving neurological impairments. However, the study does not specify the time elapsed between stroke onset and acupuncture application in the included clinical trials.

Regarding motor dysfunction, acupuncture points such as *Zusanli* (ST36) (Figure 1), located 3 cun (approximately four patient's fingers) below the patella on the lateral margin of the tibia, and *Yanglingquan* (GB34) (Figure 2), located on the lateral aspect of the leg, below and anterior to the head of the fibula, are the main points used.

Figure 1. ST36 acupuncture point. Source: World Health Organization²⁰.

These are frequently applied to treat muscular flaccidity of the lower limbs. Their therapeutic action includes opening meridians, activating collaterals and muscles, relaxing tendons, and facilitating joint movement. Mechanistically, they contribute to improved muscle structure, promotion of neural remodelling, and enhancement of functional brain connectivity²¹.

For stroke-induced swallowing disorders, as illustrated in Figure 3, the point *Lianquan* (CV23), located on the anterior midline of the neck, just superior to the hyoid bone, is used to treat dysphagia, aphasia, loss of voice, hoarseness, and other pharyngeal conditions. Its therapeutic effects are achieved by improving the swallowing response signal and increasing localised blood flow in the cortex²¹.

Figure 2. GB34 acupuncture point. Source: World Health Organization ²⁰.

Figure 3. CV23 acupuncture point. Source: World Health Organization ²⁰.

The local acupuncture points *Jianliao* (TE14) (Figure 4) and *Jianyu* (LI15) (Figure 5), located respectively on the upper arm and lateral aspect of the shoulder, are effective for treating paralytic conditions such as shoulder and arm pain, paralysis of the upper limbs, and shoulder joint contracture ²¹.

Figure 4. TE14 acupuncture point. Source: World Health Organization ²⁰.

Figure 5. LI15 acupuncture point. Source: World Health Organization ²⁰.

The point *Baihui* (GV20) (Figure 6), located at the vertex of the head, is used to stimulate the brain and open the mind, treating depression and cognitive disorders. Additionally, GV20 significantly improves inflammatory responses and metabolic disturbances in the brain, while maintaining the integrity of the hippocampal areas and white matter ²¹.

Figure 6. GV20 acupuncture point. Source: World Health Organization ²⁰.

Figure 7. HT5 acupuncture point. Source: World Health Organization ²⁰.

Furthermore, the Heart meridian, primarily associated with cardiothoracic and psychosomatic disorders, uses the point *Tongli* (HT5) (Figure 7) for conditions such as aphasia, dysarthria, and hoarseness. HT5 plays a key role in improving language function by activating Broca's area and facilitating the dynamic connectivity of the neurolinguistic network²¹.

According to Wang *et al.*²², the three most frequently selected acupuncture points are *Shuigou* (GV26), GV20, and *Neiguan* (PC6). One study compared the effects of these three points with Quchi (LI11), GB34, and *Sanyinjiao* (SP6) in rats with middle cerebral artery occlusion. The results indicated that electroacupuncture at GV26 and GV20 produced the most significant effects, markedly increasing cerebral blood flow, with perfusion synchronised to electrical stimulation. In another study, acupuncture was applied at GV26, PC6, SP6, *Chize* (LU5), and *Weizhong* (BL40) in rats with middle cerebral artery occlusion. The findings revealed that only GV26 and PC6 had significant effects on restoring cerebral blood flow. Additionally, the group of points from the Pericardium meridian (*Quze* PC3 and PC6) showed significantly superior outcomes compared with the Large Intestine meridian points (*Hegu* LI4 and LI11) in promoting microangiogenesis (formation of new blood vessels).

Figure 8. Location of acupuncture points according to Wang *et al.*²². Source: Wang *et al.*²².

In a review by Chang *et al.*¹⁸, the most commonly used acupuncture points for neuroprotection and neuroregeneration were: LI4; *Shousanli* (LI10); LI11; LI15; *Jugu* (LI16); *Futu* (ST32); ST36; *Shangjuxu* (ST37); *Fenglong* (ST40); SP6; BL23 (*Shenshu*); PC6; *Waiguan* (TE5); *Qubin* (GB7); *Fengchi* (GB20); *Taichong* (LR3); *Chengjiang* (CV24); *Mingmen* (GV4); *Jinsuo* (GV8); *Shendao* (GV11); *Fengfu* (GV16); GV20; *Shenting* (GV24); *Renzhong* (GV26).

Improving neurological function has become a key research focus in cerebrovascular diseases in recent years. Acupuncture, recognised by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a treatment for stroke, has gained broad application due to its simplicity, absence of significant side effects, and effectiveness in improving prognosis and quality of life in stroke patients²³.

According to Lam Ching *et al.*²⁴, patients with post-stroke depression often experience anxiety, despair, and insomnia, which negatively affect daily activities and overall

rehabilitation. Their study suggests that acupuncture, used either alone or in combination with other treatments, appears beneficial in improving post-stroke depressive symptoms. Moreover, when compared with Western medicine, acupuncture, whether used alone or combined, demonstrated greater efficacy in alleviating these complaints.

Finally, Yamamoto New Scalp Acupuncture (YNSA) applies points located on the scalp (frontal, parietal, and occipital regions), based on somatotopic correspondence areas. These include the Basic A points (A1 for shoulder, A2 for elbow, A3 for hand), commonly used in post-stroke hemiparesis; the Basic B points (B1–B6), each corresponding to a body region (B1 – contralateral upper limb, B2 – contralateral lower limb, B3–B5 – upper trunk, head, and neck), useful in post-stroke hemiplegia; and the Basic C points, which assist in postural control and balance. The Ypsilon (Y) points, associated with internal organ dysfunctions and chronic conditions, are frequently applied in systemic impairments after stroke to modulate motor, sensory, and cognitive functions. These are particularly valuable in post-stroke rehabilitation where spasticity or sensorimotor deficits are present. The Cerebral points activate cortical function and are used to treat paralysis, aphasia, cognitive alterations, motor disorders (hemiplegia, paraplegia), dizziness, vertigo, visual disturbances, tinnitus, epilepsy, sleep disorders, depression, and chronic pain ²⁵.

3.2. Herbal Medicine

Herbal medicine is defined as the use of medicinal plants and their extracts to prevent, alleviate, or treat disease ²⁶. Recent research has focused on the potential of natural substances derived from fruits and vegetables to prevent motor or sensory deficits resulting from cerebral ischemia. For this reason, various plants and their components were investigated for their potential to protect against cerebral ischemia or to alleviate post-stroke neurological disorders ^{10,27}. This study identifies and analyses traditional medicines for the treatment of ischemic stroke, highlighting their species, families, medicinal parts, and pharmacological effects. Most of these medicines are botanical in origin, distributed among 132 families, with *Leguminosae* being the most common. Several widely used plants were identified, such as *Ligusticum chuanxiong*, safflower, *Angelica sinensis*, and musk. Multiple pharmacological, phytochemical, and clinical studies have been used to evaluate their biological activity and mechanisms of action. Among their compounds, ligustrazine, ferulic acid, hydroxysafflor, and yellow A stand out as promising candidates due to their neuroprotective effects ²⁷. Nevertheless, future research may further explore new therapeutic possibilities by studying the components and mechanisms of these traditional preparations.

Chinese patent medicines with distinct primary ingredients, including *Salvia miltiorrhiza*, *Ginkgo biloba*, and *Panax notoginseng*, are among the most commonly prescribed treatments for stroke sequelae. The integration of antihypertensives in combination with *Salvia miltiorrhiza* appears to be the most widespread combined therapy ²⁸.

Following a stroke, neuronal and other brain tissue injury triggers an inflammatory response. Microglia (a type of glial cell in the central nervous system) are among the first cells to respond, becoming activated to counteract the inflammation. Traditional Chinese medicines influence microglial activation and polarisation, thereby reducing inflammatory responses and alleviating neuronal injury through the involvement of microglia and various related pathways ²⁹.

Traditionally, the root of *Angelica gigas Nakai* (*Umbelliferae*) has also been used for the treatment of ischemic diseases and is considered safe for human use, particularly in ischemic stroke therapy ³⁰.

According to Seto *et al.* ³¹, medicines capable of stimulating angiogenesis (the biological process of forming new blood vessels from existing ones) after ischemic stroke may offer therapeutic advantages in treatment. Several studies have demonstrated the pro-angiogenic effects of different Chinese herbs and herbal preparations in both in vitro and in vivo settings, as reported by Zhang *et al.* ³² and Zhang *et al.* ³³.

Table 1 provides a concise summary of some classical Chinese formulas used in post-stroke rehabilitation, along with their corresponding differential diagnosis patterns, typical symptoms, common modifications, and available scientific references.

Table 1. Examples of herbal medicine used in post-stroke rehabilitation, according to TCM diagnosis.

TCM Pattern	Classical Formula	Main Actio	Typical Post-Stroke Symptoms	Common Modifications	Ref.
Wind-Fire Disturbance	<i>Tian Ma Gou Teng Yin</i> (modified)	Calms the Liver, extinguishes Wind, tonifies the Kidneys	Tremors, dizziness, muscle rigidity, and associated hypertension	Variations according to individual symptoms	34
Phlegm-Stasis Blocking Collaterals	<i>Ban Xia Bai Zhu Tian Ma + Tao Hong Si Wu</i> (modified)	Eliminates Phlegm, tonifies, and improves circulation	Hemiplegia, dysarthria, limb rigidity	Combined with ingredients for phlegm and stasis	34
Qi Deficiency with Blood Stasis	<i>Bu Yang Huan Wu Tang</i> (modified)	Tonifies Qi, moves Blood, unblocks channels	Muscle weakness, hemiplegia, paresthesia, slow recovery	Adjustments according to Qi or Blood signs	34
Neuroprotection / Multiple Mechanisms	Other formulas and components, such as safranal, ginkgo, Buyang Huanwu + antioxidants	Neuroprotection via anti-inflammatory, antioxidative, and regenerative modulation	Functional improvement, quality of life, and brain connectivity	Complex, syndrome-dependent	35

These formulas, as described in the table, do not replace individualised clinical evaluation, as the ideal treatment always requires a precise diagnosis followed by personalisation of the classical formula (including additions, increases, or dosage reductions). The most effective approach is to complement these formulas with motor rehabilitation, acupuncture, dietotherapy, and conventional medical follow-up, thereby optimising the potential integrative benefits.

3.3. Qigong

Qigong is a practice that integrates gentle and deliberate movements, meditative exercises, and breathing techniques with the aim of enhancing the flow of vital energy³⁶. Its practice offers multiple advantages for physical and mental health, including improved digestive function, enhanced circulatory performance, increased immunity, better sleep quality, relaxation of the body and mind, improved mood, greater tranquillity, pleasure, and symptom relief. At the same time, *qigong* is considered an appropriate form of exercise for older adults. These findings suggest that *qigong* may be a beneficial and practical mind–body exercise that promotes overall health and reduces the risk of stroke³⁷.

The study by Yang *et al.*³⁸ further suggests that *qigong* exercises improve the quality of life in stroke patients and have beneficial effects on limb coordination and balance function. In this study, the *qigong* group practised *Baduanjin* exercises (gentle postures and movements coordinated with breathing and mental focus) three times per week, for 40 minutes per session, as part of their medical or regular rehabilitation program. Each session included a 5–10 minute warm-up and relaxation routine focused on stretching, rhythmic breathing, and relaxation, followed by 30 minutes of *qigong* practice incorporating movements and repetitions.

3.4. Moxibustion

Moxibustion is a therapeutic method that uses certain substances or herbs, most notably *Artemisia vulgaris*, to warm acupuncture points or specific body areas targeted for treatment. The heat generated produces stimuli that regulate physiological functions

through the meridians³⁹. Similar to acupuncture, moxibustion employs different techniques to stimulate points where *Qi* accumulates, potentially influencing nerve regeneration in various brain regions. The selected points are generally specific acupuncture points, chosen according to the patient's condition and therapeutic objectives¹⁷.

Moxibustion has demonstrated beneficial effects in relieving pain, supporting limb rehabilitation, increasing blood flow, and activating cerebral lobes with reduced perfusion, as well as promoting neuronal reorganisation in patients suffering from ischemic stroke¹⁸. Additionally, Liu *et al.*⁴⁰ reported that moxibustion may promote axonal regeneration and improve learning and memory in post-stroke cognitive deficits.

3.5. Cupping Therapy

Cupping therapy involves placing cups on the skin using heat or suction for several minutes. This vacuum effect draws the skin and underlying tissues upward, producing localised suction and initiating a localised healing response. Cupping therapy is employed to relieve pain, such as in migraine, carpal tunnel syndrome, and several other localised conditions, including post-stroke sequelae⁴¹.

The results of Kim *et al.*⁴¹ indicate the potential of cupping therapy as a beneficial treatment for various post-stroke complications. Specifically, cupping combined with bloodletting as an adjunctive therapy for stroke patients showed considerable improvements in motor function and upper-limb spasticity, supported by a moderate level of evidence.

Similarly, Shao *et al.*⁴² suggested that cupping therapy combined with rehabilitation training should be included in a comprehensive therapeutic protocol for stroke patients with upper-limb spasticity. However, due to the high risk of bias and heterogeneity of the included studies, the antispastic efficacy of this combination requires further validation.

Additionally, Ali *et al.*⁴³ confirmed that a polyherbal Unani formulation (*Munzija wa Mus'hil Balgham*) combined with dry cupping was considered effective in treating post-stroke sequelae.

3.6. Tui Na Massage

Tui Na massage is a therapeutic form of bodywork aimed at balancing the flow of *Qi* and blood through the body's meridians, thereby promoting healing and supporting both physical and emotional well-being⁴⁴.

The review by Cabanas-Valdés *et al.*⁴⁵ indicated that Chinese therapeutic massage (*Tui Na*), when combined with standard physiotherapy, is an effective non-invasive approach for improving motor function in the upper and lower limbs and reducing spasticity, particularly during the subacute phase of stroke recovery.

Furthermore, according to Chen *et al.*⁴⁶, the integration of *Tui Na* with functional near-infrared spectroscopy may provide insights into the functional condition of sensorimotor neuronal circuits. Changes in neuroactivity within the sensorimotor cortex observed during *Tui Na* applied at the acupuncture point LI4 (located on the dorsum of the hand, between the thumb and index finger – Figure 9) suggest a specific relationship between acupuncture points in TCM and neuronal circuitry.

Figure 9. LI4 acupuncture point. Source: World Health Organization 20.

Wang *et al.*⁴⁷ reported that *Tui Na* massage is safe and effective in reducing upper-limb spasticity following stroke when administered within 1 to 3 months post-event. The study also found that a 4-week course of *Tui Na* treatment for upper-limb spasticity yielded improvements that persisted for up to 6 months after the conclusion of therapy.

3.7. Dietotherapy

Dietotherapy is a therapeutic approach that uses nutrition as a means of preventing, treating, or managing disease. Dietary patterns may represent a risk factor in individuals predisposed to stroke or with associated risk factors that increase the probability of stroke occurrence. Accordingly, dietary adjustments for stroke patients should be implemented both during hospitalisation and throughout post-hospital recovery. Ensuring adequate nutrition and incorporating naturally derived compounds is essential in post-stroke management due to their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective, and neuroplasticity-promoting properties⁴⁸.

Moreover, comprehensive TCM interventions for patients with post-stroke depression have been shown to be beneficial in improving quality of life, with dietotherapy playing a fundamental role in this integrative therapeutic framework⁴⁹.

4. Discussion

This narrative review synthesised the available evidence on various TCM therapeutic techniques in the management of post-stroke sequelae. Overall, acupuncture was the most frequently investigated intervention, although the consistency and magnitude of reported effects varied across studies. While most trials suggest benefits in neurological recovery, improved quality of life, and relief of post-stroke depression, some studies did not observe significant differences compared to conventional therapies. This indicates that positive outcomes may depend on factors such as session frequency, practitioner expertise, and the rehabilitation phase in which the patient is treated^{18,19}. Although most of the articles analysed in this review did not provide specific guidance on the timing of acupuncture initiation after stroke, the broader scientific literature suggests that it may be beneficial even in later stages of recovery, with earlier initiation showing greater efficacy. Several studies indicate that acupuncture started within the first 24–48 hours post-stroke leads to better motor and functional recovery, provided the patient's clinical condition allows for

early intervention⁵⁰. Zhang *et al.*²¹ reported treatment durations ranging from 2 to 6 weeks, but did not specify the time interval between stroke onset and the start of therapy.

In herbal medicine, plants such as *Ligusticum chuanxiong*, *Angelica sinensis*, and *Salvia miltiorrhiza* have been described as having antioxidant and neuroprotective properties. However, formulations, dosages, and combinations varied substantially across trials, limiting direct comparisons and the extrapolation of findings. The use of *Angelica gigas Nakai* root showed promise in ischemic stroke, although evidence is primarily derived from experimental or small-scale clinical studies^{10,11,28,30}. Current literature suggests that Chinese herbal medicine should ideally be initiated in the early subacute phase (7 days to 3 months post-stroke), particularly within 26 to 62 days of the event, especially when integrated with acupuncture and conventional rehabilitation⁵⁰.

Qigong, moxibustion, cupping therapy, and *Tui Na* massage demonstrated functional and symptomatic improvements. Nevertheless, the heterogeneity of protocols and scarcity of high-quality controlled trials limit the strength of these conclusions. In some cases, such as cupping therapy, reported benefits may be partly attributable to placebo effects or concurrent complementary treatments^{36,38,41,42,46}. *Tui Na* massage was found to be effective and safe when initiated within the first 3 months after stroke, particularly between 1 and 3 months, with reduced efficacy if applied later⁴⁷.

Finally, dietotherapy, often combined with herbal formulations, provides antioxidant and neuroprotective benefits. However, most studies did not isolate its effects from those of other interventions, making it difficult to determine its specific contribution^{48,49}.

Although current evidence supports the potential of TCM as an adjunct in post-stroke rehabilitation, findings should be interpreted with caution. Randomised controlled trials with larger sample sizes, standardised protocols, and long-term follow-up are necessary to confirm and quantify the observed effects.

Future research should aim to: (1) define standardized intervention protocols (frequency, duration, intensity, and therapeutic combinations) to enable consistent comparisons across studies; (2) explore personalized treatment strategies, tailoring TCM techniques to the clinical profiles and individual needs of patients; and (3) conduct multicentre randomized controlled trials with representative samples and long-term follow-up to evaluate not only immediate efficacy but also sustained outcomes.

Ongoing research and collaboration between Western medicine and TCM may generate new therapeutic insights, contributing to the development of more comprehensive and individualised approaches for stroke treatment.

5. Conclusion

The investigation of TCM techniques in stroke rehabilitation indicates promising potential to enhance conventional treatments, providing effective strategies with minimal adverse effects.

Acupuncture, cupping therapy, moxibustion, *Tui Na* massage, herbal medicine, *qigong*, and dietotherapy all show beneficial impacts on neurological function, reducing inflammation, improving quality of life, and supporting recovery from post-stroke sequelae.

Nevertheless, despite advances in understanding the mechanisms underlying these therapies, further comprehensive studies using rigorous methodologies are still required to confirm their efficacy and facilitate integration into clinical practice.

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